

Supplemental Figure 2

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SI Figure 2: Western blot analysis of cleaved-caspase-3 along the intestines. Western blots were used to detect protein level of cleaved-caspase-3 in small (ileum) and large (cecum, proximal and distal colon) intestinal epithelial cells of saline-controlled and HDE-exposed mice. Densitometry of the bands were normalized to beta-actin and is expressed as a ratio. After 15 days of HDE exposure, cleaved-caspase-3 protein expression in the ileum (17kda, $p=0.4286$; 19kda, $p=0.4286$; $n=5-6$ /group), cecum (17kda, $p=0.6623$; 19kda, $p=0.5368$; $n=5-6$ /group), proximal (17kda, $p<0.05$; $n=5-6$ /group) and distal colon (17kda, $p=0.1255$; $n=5-6$ /group) did not

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differ between groups. Differences in groups were compared by Mann Whitney U test. The sex of each mouse is depicted by the data point color (light/pink (female) or light/blue (male)).